

Peroxydisulphate Oxidation of Steroidal Olefins[†]

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Oxidation of some steroidal olefins with $K_2S_2O_8$ proceeded very smoothly in acetic acid without any catalyst. Cholest-5-ene (1) and its 3 β -acetoxy (1a), 3 β -chloro (1b) analogues provided the corresponding 6-ketones (2, 2b) along with some additional products (3-3d). Cholest-3,5-diene (4) afforded the diones (5, 5a) and 6-nitrocholesta-3,5-diene (4a) yielded some new interesting compounds (6, 7-7c) in which nitrocholest-5-ene moiety remained unaffected. The structures of the products have been established on the basis of their analytical and spectral (ir, 1H nmr, mass) data.

PEROXYDISULPHATE has been used as a successful reagent for the oxidation of various types of organic compounds¹⁻³ but its use in the field of steroids is rather limited⁴⁻⁷. In order to investigate the oxidative action of potassium peroxydisulphate, some steroidal olefins were selected and the results are presented in this communication. Potassium peroxydisulphate oxidation of cholest-5-ene (1) in presence of acetic acid yielded 5 α -cholestan-6-one (2)⁸ and 5-hydroxy-6 β -acetoxy-5 α -cholestane (3)⁸ as the major products. Similar oxidation of 3 β -substituted-cholest-5-enes (1a and 1b) gave the corresponding 6-keto (2a and 2b)^{9,10} and 5 α -hydroxy-6 β -acetoxy derivatives (3a and 3b)^{11,12}. The oxidation products of 3 β -hydroxycholest-5-ene (1c) were identical with those obtained from 1a, obviously due to prior acetylation of the hydroxyl group under the reaction condition. It, however, provided two additional compounds which were identified as 3c and 3d¹³. When cholesta-3,5-diene (4) was oxidised with this reagent, the products obtained were cholest-4-en-3,6-dione (5)¹⁴ and its dihydro derivative (5a)¹⁵. Insertion of a nitro group at 6-position of this diene modified the course of reaction and thus peroxydisulphate oxidation of 6-nitrocholesta-3,5-diene (4a) afforded 3 α -acetoxy-4 α -oxa-A-homo-6-nitrocholesta-5-en-4-one (6), the nitrodiol (7) and its mono- and diacetates (7a-7c).

- 3 ; X=H R=OH, R'=OAc, R''=H
3a ; X=OAc, R=OH, R'=OAc, R''=H
3b ; X=Cl, R=OH, R'=OAc, R''=H
3c ; X=OAc, R=OH, R'=OH, R''=H
3d ; X=OAc, R=OH, R'=H, R''=OAc

- 4 ; R=H
4a ; R=NO₂ 5
5a ; 4,5-dihydro

- 7 ; R=OH, R'=OH
7a ; R=OAc, R'=OH
7b ; R=OH, R'=OAc
7c ; R=OAc, R'=OAc
8 ; X=H
8a ; X=OAc
8b ; X=Cl

- 1 ; X=H
1a ; X=OAc
1b ; X=Cl
1c ; X=OH

- 2 ; X=H
2a ; X=OAc
2b ; X=Cl

From an inspection of the reaction products, it was logically conjectured that the persulphate oxidation of the steroidal olefins proceeded through the formation of epoxides and this assumption was proved to be correct from the observation that 5 α ,6 α -epoxide of cholest-5-ene (8) and its 3 β -substituted derivatives (8a and 8b) yielded the same products as were obtained from the corresponding

[†]Dedicated to Prof. S. M. Osman, former Chairman, Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, on the occasion of his 60th birthday.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Product Compd	M.p. (°C) Observed (Reported)	Yield %	Mol. formula	ν_{\max} (cm ⁻¹)	δ (CDCl ₃ ; TMS)
2a ^a	128 (127-29)	52	C ₂₉ H ₄₆ O ₃	1 735 (OAc), 1 705 (C=O), 1 240, 1 030 (C-O)	4.80 (3H, m, C-3 α -H; W _{1/2} 19Hz, axial), 2.0 (3H, s, OAc), 1.20-0.72 ^b
3a ^b	167 (166)	42	C ₃₁ H ₅₂ O ₅	3 500 (OH), 1 740, 1 735 (OAc), 1 265, 1 240, 1 035 (C-O)	5.10 (1H, m, C-3 α -H, W _{1/2} 18Hz, axial), 4.8 (1H, t, C-6 α -H, J _{a,e} , J _{ee} 3.2Hz, equatorial), 3.18 (1H, s, OH), 2.1 (3H, s, OAc), 1.98 (3H, s, OAc), 1.15-0.70 ^b
2b ^c	128 (128-29)	19	C ₂₇ H ₄₅ ClO	1 710 (C=O), 760 (C-Cl)	3.7 (1H, m, C-3 α -H, W _{1/2} 18Hz, axial), 1.22-0.74 ^b
3b ^d	151 (150-51)	34	C ₂₉ H ₄₉ ClO ₃	3 480 (OH), 1 725 (OAc), 1 260, 1 030 (C-O), 760 (C-Cl)	4.75 (1H, t, C-6 α -H, J _{ee} , J _{ea} 3.6Hz, equatorial), 4.25 (1H, m, C-3 α -H, W _{1/2} 16Hz), 2.15 (3H, s, OAc), 2.0 (1H, s, OH), 1.11-0.70 ^b
3d ^e	208 (209)	3	C ₃₁ H ₅₂ O ₅	3 460 (OH), 1 740, 1 730 (OAc), 1 260, 1 250, 1 030 (C-O)	5.2 (1H, m, C-3 α -H, W _{1/2} 18Hz, axial), 4.7 (1H, dd, C-6 β -H, J _{a,e} , J _{aa} 13Hz, axial), 2.1 (3H, s, OAc), 1.98 (3H, s, OAc), 1.2-0.75 ^b
3c ^e	187 (188)	7	C ₂₉ H ₅₀ O ₄	3 480, 3 420 (OH), 1 725 (OAc), 1 255, 1 035 (C-O)	5.1 (3H, m, W _{1/2} 18Hz, axial), 4.5 (1H, t, C-6 α -H, J _{ee} , J _{ea} 3.3Hz, equatorial), 2.05 (3H, s, OAc), 1.98 (1H, s, OH), 1.25-0.71 ^b
5 ^f	123 (124-25)	43	C ₂₇ H ₄₂ O ₂	1 690 (C=O), 1 675 (C=C-C=O), 1 615 (C=C)	6.0 (1H, s, C-4-vinyl-H), 1.28-0.76 ^b
5a ^g	166 (168)	37	C ₂₇ H ₄₄ O ₂	1 720 (C=O)	2.7-2.0 (7H, br, hump protons (α -H), 1.25-0.75 ^b
6	Oil ^f	6	C ₂₉ H ₄₈ NO ₆	1 780 (C=O, enol-lactone), 1 745 (OAc), 1 678 (C=C), 1 530, 1 370 (NO ₂), 1 230, 1 060 (C-O)	5.5 (1H, m, C-3 α -H, W _{1/2} 7Hz, equatorial), 2.0 (3H, s, OAc), 1.21-0.70 ^b
7	126	9	C ₂₇ H ₄₅ NO ₄ (M ⁺ : 447)	3 400 (OH), 1 620 (C=C), 1 525, 1 375 (NO ₂)	4.41 (1H, d, C-4 α -H, J 3Hz, equatorial), 4.03 (1H, m, C-3 β -H, W _{1/2} 6Hz, equatorial), 2.4 (2H, br, OH), 1.26-0.75 ^b
7a	117	32	C ₂₉ H ₄₇ NO ₅ (M ⁺ : 489)	3 400 (OH), 1 725 (OAc), 1 630 (C=C), 1 530, 1 375 (NO ₂), 1 040 (C-O)	4.9 (1H, m, C-3 β -H, W _{1/2} 5Hz, equatorial), 4.2 (1H, d, C-4 α -H, J 4Hz, equatorial), 2.4 (1H, s, OH), 2.1 (3H, s, OAc), 1.23-0.72 ^b
7b	167	32	C ₂₉ H ₄₇ NO ₅ (M ⁺ : 489)	3 490 (OH), 1 740 (OAc), 1 630 (C=C), 1 530, 1 370 (NO ₂), 1 240, 1 050 (C-O)	5.4 (1H, d, C-4 α -H, J 3Hz, equatorial), 3.95 (1H, m, C-3 β -H, W _{1/2} 6Hz, equatorial), 2.6 (1H, s, OH), 2.0 (3H, s, OAc), 1.20-0.70 ^b
7c	Oil	17	C ₃₁ H ₄₉ NO ₆ (M ⁺ : 531)	1 745 (OAc), 1 630 (C=C), 1 520, 1 370 (NO ₂), 1 230, 1 030 (C-O)	5.4 (1H, d, C-4 α -H, J 4Hz, equatorial), 4.9 (1H, m, C-3 β -H, W _{1/2} 4.5 Hz, equatorial), 2.0 (2 \times 3H, s, OAc), 1.25-0.70 ^b

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses. ^aRef. 9. ^bRef. 10. ^cRef. 11. ^dRef. 12. ^eRef. 13. ^fRef. 14. ^gRef. 15. ^hAngular and side-chain methyl protons.

olefins. It is interesting to note that the nitro group and the double bond between 5,6-position remained intact in all the reaction products of 4a, presumably due to the high oxidation state of nitroolefinic group. In support of this assumption it was observed that peroxydisulphate failed to oxidise 6-nitrocholest-5-ene and its 3 β -acetoxy derivative. For the sake of chemical justification, the compounds 7-7c were converted into each other by employing acetylation and hydrolysis methods.

The physical and spectral data of compounds are presented in Table I.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam

SP3-100 spectrometer, ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian A-60D instrument with TMS as the internal standard and mass spectra on a JMS-D 300 spectrometer at 70 eV. Column chromatography was performed with silica gel (60-120 mesh). Tlc plates were coated with silica gel and a 20% aqueous perchloric acid was used as the spraying agent. Light petroleum (b.p. 40-60°) was used.

Peroxydisulphate oxidation of 1. General procedure: A mixture of 1 (13.49 mmol) and K₂S₂O₈ (4.19 mmol) in acetic acid (100 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature, filtered and diluted with water. The organic mass was extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed several times with water, aqueous NaHCO₃ solution (5%) and water successively and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. After

the removal of the solvent, an oil was obtained which was chromatographed over silica gel (80 g). Elution with light petroleum ether-ether (40 : 1) gave the steroidal ketone (2) which was recrystallised from methanol, (28.74%), m.p. 97° (lit.² 98–100°) (Found: C, 83.98; H, 11.87. $C_{27}H_{46}O$ requires: C, 83.94; H, 11.91%); ν_{\max} 1705 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ 1.19 (3H, s, C-10-CH₃), 0.68 (3H, s, C-13-CH₃), 0.90 and 0.81 (other methyl protons). Further elution with petroleum ether-ether (30 : 1) afforded as an oil which was crystallised from methanol, (36.53%), m.p. 109°, (lit.⁸ 108°) (Found: C, 78.00; H, 11.27. $C_{29}H_{50}O_3$ requires: C, 78.03; H, 11.21%); ν_{\max} 3500 (OH), 1730, 1240 (COO acetate) and 1030 cm^{-1} (C–O); δ 4.7 (1H, t, $J_{ee}=J_{ea}=3.2$ Hz, C-6 α -H), 2.0 (3H, s, CH₃COO), 1.98 (1H, s, OH D₂O exchangeable), 1.17 (3H, s, C-10-CH₃), 0.71 (s, C-13-CH₃), 0.93 and 0.84 (other methyl protons).

Oxidation reactions of the steroidal olefins (1a–1c, 4, 4a) and α -epoxides (8–8b) with potassium peroxydisulphate were carried out under identical reaction conditions.

Acetylation of 3 α ,4 β -dihydroxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (7), 3 α -acetoxy-4 β -hydroxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (7a) and 3 α -hydroxy-4 β -acetoxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (7b): Each of the compounds 7 (0.67 mmol), 7a (0.61 mmol) and 7b (0.61 mmol) was dissolved separately in purified pyridine (1.5 ml) and freshly distilled acetic anhydride (1.2 ml). All the mixtures were heated at 50° for 3 h. Each mixture was poured in cold water, the resulting solids were taken in ether, washed and dried. From every reaction, compound 7c was obtained in ~65% yield.

Hydrolysis of 7a, 7b and 3 α ,4 β -diacetoxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (7c): Each of the compounds 7a

(0.41 mmol), 7b (0.41 mmol) and 7c (0.37 mmol) was dissolved in ethanol (10 ml) separately and 36% HCl (2 ml) was added in each reaction mixture. All the mixtures were refluxed for 1 h. Half of the alcohol was then evaporated from each mixture, diluted with water, extracted with ether and worked up. From every reaction, compound 7 was obtained in 80, 75 and 60% yields, respectively.

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